

The Effect of Teaching Methods on Attitude and Retention of Co-Education and Single-Sex Students in Senior School Biology

CLEOPAS C. Blessing (PhD)

Department of Science Education
Faculty of Education, Federal University, Otuoke
Bayelsa State
chinyerecleopas@yahoo.com
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&

Prof. IGBOJINWAEKWU C. Patrick

Department of Science Education
Faculty of Education, Niger Delta University
Bayelsa State
earimeka@gmail.com

Abstract

This study investigated effect of teaching methods on attitude and retention of co-education and single-sex students in senior school biology, using quasi-experimental research design. The teaching methods used were demonstration, discussion and lecture methods. The population was made up of 6,988 Senior Secondary School Students 2. The sample size was 323 Senior School Two students from 23 Senior Secondary Schools in Yenagoa and Ogbia Local Government Areas. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. Three instruments guided the conduct of the study namely, Discussion, Demonstration and Lecture Methods. Standardized Biology Achievement Test, Students' Retention Level Test and Students' Learning Attitude were adopted as reliable instruments for data collection. Percentage, mean, standard deviation and z-test statistics were used for analysis of data. The findings revealed that no significant difference in the mean scores of SS2 students in single-sex and co-education schools in attitude when taught with demonstration, discussion and lecture teaching methods in Biology. Also, no significant difference in the mean scores of SS2 students in single-sex and co-education schools taught with demonstration method in retention level enhancement in Biology. There is a substantial variance in the mean scores of students in single-sex schools taught with demonstration and lecture teaching methods and discussion and lecture methods in retention level enhancement in Biology. Recommendations made include that teachers should give adequate consideration to teaching methods in biology to enhance students' attitude and retention, hence, improved academic performance in Biology.

Keywords: Discussion, Demonstration, Methods, Attitude, Retention.

Introduction

Education has become a veritable tool for measuring advancement in science and technology in any nation in contemporary times. It is the inculcation of knowledge, skills, values, morals and attitudes to a learner in order to have a change in behaviour that will be of help to him or her and to the society. The swiftness at which knowledge is growing due to scientific and technological discovery is not equal to rise in attitude to science. This has become a worry that calls for attention

in education community in recent times. Attitude is our view, manner, conduct or predisposition to changes influenced by environment, experiences, observation and background. All learners have prior knowledge and experiences based on observation, background and their environment (McLeod, 2019). This background knowledge interferes in teaching and learning positively or negatively. Ahmad and Asghar (2011) defined attitude as a state of mind in response to views, ideas, people, place and happenings around them. They opined that the concept of attitude has diverse explanations based on people's views. George (as cited in Ahmad & Asghar, 2011) and Ogunleye and Fasakin (2011) opined that students' manner is a major factor in education as regards choice of subject and development of positive science attitude that improves interest in science courses. Negative attitude of learners could make learners to be away from classes, absent-minded and uninterested about lessons because they dislike the teacher and these will lead to poor academic achievement (Cleopas & Igbojinwaekwu, 2023). Motivation to science, fear of failure of science and academic achievement in science, students' attitude to science which include fear of science, view of science teacher, value of science, fun of science, parents' attitude towards science, nature of environment to do science, peer group attitude to science, self-concept at science, among others are measures of attitude used by researchers over the years (Ahmad & Asghar, 2011; Arokoyu & Chukwu, 2017).

Hussaini et al (2015) and Yousuf and Bhutta (2012) asserted that school type contributes to poor performance in students' academic, attitude and retention. This is in support of the work of Oginni et al (2013) and in contrast of works of Ndu et al, 2005; Isah et al, 2019 who admitted that school type has no substantial influence on academic achievement, attitude and retention of students in biology. Gender issue such as complex problem affects single-sex schools' academic achievement, attitude and retention (Ademe, 2016; Teba, 2020). This is in disagreement with Igbojinwaekwu (as cited in Igbojinwaekwu & Torunarigha, 2012) in his work that girls' school students do not have complex issue anymore since more female teachers are teachers of sciences in contemporary times. Several works are available on co-education schools as having an edge on single-sex schools in terms of academic achievement, attitude and retention due to exchange of ideas, thoughts, socialization as a result of its nature (Ademe, 2016; Igbojinwaekwu as cited in Igbojinwaekwu & Torunarigha, 2012), but there is little empirical evidence on single-sex schools and their comparison with co-education schools in terms of academic achievement, attitude and retention in Biology.

Retention is the capacity to hold ideas or information. The ability to remember and continue to use ideas or information acquired during and after learning when called to do so. One of the reasons for poor academic achievement is low level of retention in students. Aminu (as cited in Gongden, 2022) listed several variables that affect retention level which include students previous experience, interval between lesson and evaluation, task to be performed, instructional approaches employed and method of teaching used.

Basil & Jajua (2019) defined discussion method as a teaching strategy that involves interaction, communication and exchange of ideas and opinions among students and between students and teachers. Discussion method of teaching is an interactive session between the teacher and the learners, among the learners, between groups of students or among groups of students. The teacher acts as a facilitator or guidance into discovery of new information. It is a method that enhances active participation and interaction, group work, exchange of ideas and thoughts in the class, healthy relationship among learners and between teachers and learners and a team spirit. McLeod (2018) opined that learning is active, interactive, participatory, collaborative and dynamic.

Demonstration method is the presentation, exhibition and dramatization of lessons by the teachers to the students in the laboratory or classroom or field in the teaching and learning process. Demonstration method involves display of sketches, diagrams, charts, video presentations, models and real life specimen in teaching and learning (Basil & Jajua, 2019). Achimugu (2018) opined demonstration method as a show and exhibition of materials during lessons so as to arouse learners' interest. Also, careful introduction activities could help bridge the gap between the known and the unknown Nzewi (as cited in Igbojinwaekwu, 2012a). For learners to benefit from demonstration, simple equipment, models and real life specimen that portray real life situation should be employed. This implies that when concrete examples, real life situation and students' experiences and environment relate to biology, it becomes fun, which arouse interest in students thereby leading to higher achievement in biology (Ahmad & Asghar (2011). Demonstration method incorporates collaboration learning, cooperative method of teaching, discovery, questioning, inquiry, among others which enhances group work, students- students' interaction, active participation, team spirit and result oriented (Cleopas & Igbojinwaekwu, 2023).

Nwagbo & Ajaja (as cited in Oghenevwe, 2012) and Ameh and Dantani (2012) reported that teaching is commonly done by lecture method and biology is learnt in abstract, by listening, writing of notes and memorization of facts which in most cases lead to low degree of transfer of learning, lack of interest and poor academic achievement in science. Gambari et al, (2014) reported that lecture method produced higher retention level than multimedia teaching method while on the other hand, multimedia media method of teaching produced better academic achievement in students. Perhaps, this was reason lecture method has being in use till date by teachers. It is prevalent in the education system and widely used by teachers especially when class size is large (Achimugu, 2018).

Many studies abound on diverse variables such as public school students, private school students, urban school students, rural school students on academic achievement, retention, attitude, among others in biology, but, little or no studies on single-sex school students and attitude and retention of co-education and single-sex students in senior school biology in Yenagoa and Ogbia Local Government Areas in Bayelsa State, hence, the literature gap, empirical gap and population gaps. This is the why of the study, the effect of teaching methods on attitude and retention of co-education and single-sex students in senior school biology in Yenagoa and Ogbia Local Government Areas, Bayelsa State.

Statement of the Problem

The teaching and learning process of science is still a matter of concern to students, teachers, parents and stakeholders in education today. The consistent rate of failure in science, biology in particular in West African Examination Council, (WAEC) has become a matter of constant deliberation in recent times. Teachers are making several moves to eradicate failure in science subjects but results so far are still unsatisfactory. Fear of science, anxiety, attitude, inappropriate use of teaching methods, teachers' characteristics, parents' characteristics, school factors, among others have been identified by researchers to contribute to poor retention of knowledge in biology. Reports have it that students have a part to play in increasing academic achievement in biology (Ali, Toriman & Gasim, 2014; Samikwo, 2013) Academic performance in biology from West African Examination Council as stated in Badmus and Omosewo (2018) revealed that from the year 2007 to 2012, about 30% of candidates who registered for the examination had credit pass

and above in biology and from the years 2013 to 2016, only about 50% of candidates who registered for the examination had credit pass and above in biology.

Table 1: Candidates Registration and Achievement in May/June Biology:2017–2022 in Nigeria

Year	Total Sat	A1 – C6 Credit Passed	% Pass	No of Failure	% of Failure
2017	1,505,199	579,432	38.49	925,767	61.50
2018	1,340,206	383,112	28.59	957,094	71.41
2019	1,675,440	541,956	32.34	1,133,484	67.65
2020	1,433,440	371,624	26.11	1,051,812	73.89
2021	1,442,096	560,014	38.83	882,082	61.17
2022	1,249,635	415,261	33.23	834,374	66.77

Source: Adebajo and Yusuf (2023)

Data in Table 1 showed that from 2017 to 2022, percentage of candidates that had credit pass in biology returned to about 30%. This dwindling poor performance of students is worrisome to not only the education community but also to the nation (WAEC, Chief Examiner's Report, 2022). This implies that for the past one decade, less than 50% of candidates who sat for WAEC could secure admission into tertiary institutions to study science related fields career (Adebajo & Yusuf, 2022). Based on reports and studies on academic achievement of students, students' attitude toward teaching and learning of science education have been a subject that calls for attention (Ogunleye & Fasakin, 2011). It is on this background that the study sought to investigate effect of teaching methods on attitude and retention of single-sex and co-education students in senior school biology in Yenagoa and Ogbia Local Government Areas.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to ascertain the difference that exist between the mean attitude and retention scores of SS2 students in single-sex and co-education schools taught biology using demonstration and discussion methods.

1. determine the difference that exists between the mean attitude scores of SS2 students in single-sex and co-education schools taught Biology using demonstration and discussion methods
2. determine the difference that exists between the mean retention scores of SS2 students in single-sex and co-education schools taught Biology using demonstration and discussion methods

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What difference exists between the mean attitude scores of SS2 students in single-sex and co-education schools taught Biology using demonstration and discussion methods?
2. What difference exists between the mean retention scores of SS2 students in single-sex and co-education schools taught Biology using demonstration and discussion methods?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses guided the study:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean attitude scores of SS2 students in single-sex and co-education schools, taught Biology using demonstration and discussion methods.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean retention scores of SS2 students in single-sex and co-education schools, taught Biology using demonstration and discussion methods.

Theoretical Framework

Social Learning Theory (Bandura, 1961)

Bandura, Ross & Ross (1961) conducted a controlled experiment called Bobo doll experiment to examine whether social behavior (aggression) can be acquired by observation and imitation. Bobo doll experiment verified that children can learn social behavior such as aggression by observing and watching the behavior of the person. This finding supported Bandura (1977) social learning theory. He, also, asserted that when verbal explanation and description were made, learning was enhanced. Also, verbal instructional model and symbolic model interact together to enhance retention level, academic achievement and students' attitude towards learning. Verbal instructional model is the explanation of a concept in a manner that the learner will understand it better. Symbolic model includes characters in movies, internet, books and television programs. Bandura stated that for an observable behavior to be acquired, there must be attention, retention, reproduction and motivation. He is also of the view that social experiences, observing others will enhance acquisition of knowledge, skill, attitude and values. Social theory of learning also showed the interaction of personal factors and environmental factors tend to bring about learning and desired conduct. By implication, this theory is in conformity with the present study. Demonstration and discussion methods are two important teaching methods that employ the ideas and tenets of Bandura. During demonstration by the teacher or students, observation is done which will help students to understand, store/retain and recall more during test or examination. It also enhances communication skill in teaching and learning. When discussion method is used, verbal instruction model is applied which fosters active participation, interaction, communication and exchange of ideas to facilitate students' attitude, retention of ideas and concept, hence, positive attitude and retention of lessons are enhanced as opined by Bandura.

Research Method

This study adopted a pretest-posttest control group quasi-experimental research design. This was because complete randomization was not feasible due to involvement of intact classes (Thyer, 2012; Campbell, Stanley & Gage, 1963). The total population of senior school two (SS2) students was 6,988 which consisted of 3,819 male and 3,169 female students from 37 senior secondary schools in Yenagoa and Ogbia Local Government Areas in Bayelsa State. 23 schools were randomly selected from Yenagoa and Ogbia Local Government Areas. The population of SS2 Biology students in the 23 sampled schools was 779. Twenty-three schools in the two (2) local

government areas were purposively selected and randomly assigned to treatment and control group. The choice of the schools was based on the school having experienced teachers who possess teaching qualification with a minimum of three years teaching experience in Biology and teachers' willingness to participate in the experiment. The choice of the locale was based on accessibility of roads, because of the state topography and must have public, private and single-sex schools which must be motorable. Purposive selection of students was based on the fact that students were in Senior School Two (SS2), students studied Biology as a subject and students scored forty percent (40%) and above in pretest. This is to guarantee that the samples were equivalent and of equal status (Akuezuilo & Agu, 2004). To guarantee that the samples used in this study were comparable and of equal standing, 323 biology students out of 779 SS2 biology students who scored forty percent (40%) or higher on the pretest were purposefully chosen to make up the sample size. The study employed intact classes, however in order to avoid chaos in school management, pupils who received a score below 40% were kept in the class. Students had codes and wrote their first names on the script for easy identification by the researcher.

The scripts of students who scored below 40% were not used for the research, although, all eligible students did the tests but not all the students were part of the sample. Three validated and reliable instructional guides namely Discussion Teaching Method Guide (DTMG), Instructional Guide on Demonstration Teaching Method (IGDTM) and Guide on Lecture Teaching Method (GLTM). Three instruments were used in the study namely Standardized Biology Achievement Test (SBAT), Students' Retention Level Test (SRLT) and Students' Learning Attitude (SLA). The SBAT was adapted from West African Examination Council (WAEC) past questions. SRLT comprised the same items used for Students' Biology Achievement Test (SBAT). After two weeks of administration of SBAT to students, the researcher re-shuffled the same questions based on the same topics so that each question was assigned a different number and the options also, were reshuffled so that each option was assigned a different letter and re-administered the test to the same students, in order, to ascertain their retention levels. Students' Learning Attitude (SLA) was self-developed by the researcher. The reliability index of SBAT and SRLT were not calculated because the questions were not teachers' made test. According to Stanley and Hopkin (as cited in Egbule, 2002), standardized achievement tests were tests which have been processed for reliability and validity.

Therefore, standardized achievement tests are very reliable and valid, hence, they have an extensive application or usage. The determination of reliability index of SLA using Cronbach alpha yielded a reliability index coefficient of 0.9. According to Cohen, Manion and Morrison, (2011), following alpha coefficient procedures called rule of thumb, 0.9 was very extremely reliable. The pretest was administered to the students before the treatment to examine their previous knowledge of biology, attitude to biology and to provide the researcher a background knowledge of students to begin. The posttest was administered to the students after four weeks of teaching. After two weeks of post testing, retention test was administered to measure the level of retention of lesson learnt by the students. Percentage and mean were used for data analysis of research questions. Posttest mean, mean retention level, standard deviation and z-test were used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 significant level on a 2-tailed test.

Results

Research Question 1

What difference exist between the mean attitude scores of SS2 students in single-sex and co-education schools taught Biology using demonstration and discussion methods?

Table 1: Summary Mean Attitude Scores of SS2 Students in Coeducational and Single-Sex Schools Taught Biology via Demonstration, Discussion and Lecture Methods

Teaching Method	School Type	N	Pretest Attitude \bar{x}	Posttest \bar{x} Attitude \bar{x}
Demonstration	Single-sex	51	2.95	3.05
	Co-education	70	2.87	2.90
Difference			0.08	0.15
Discussion	Single-sex	26	2.82	3.10
	Co-education	89	2.94	2.96
Difference			0.12	0.14
Demonstration	Single-sex	51	2.95	3.05
Lecture		27	2.98	2.99
Difference			0.03	0.06
Demonstration	Co-education	70	2.87	2.90
Lecture		60	2.98	2.99
Difference			0.16	0.09
Discussion	Single-sex	26	2.82	3.10
Lecture		27	2.98	2.99
Difference			0.16	0.11
Discussion	Co-education	89	2.94	2.96
Lecture		60	2.98	2.99
Difference			0.04	0.03

Answer to research question one, Table 1 shows single-sex school students mean of 2.95 and co-education school students mean of 2.87 at pretest when taught with demonstration method. At posttest, when taught with demonstration method, single-sex school students had 3.05 mean and co-education school students had 2.90 mean. The slight difference in mean when taught with demonstration method was 0.15 in favour of single-sex school students. When taught with discussion method, single-sex school students had mean of 2.82 and co-education school students had mean of 2.94 at pretest. At posttest, when taught with discussion method, single-sex school students had 3.10 mean and co-education school students had 2.96 mean. The slight difference in mean when taught with discussion method was 0.14 in favour of students of single-sex schools. When taught with lecture method, single-sex school students had mean of 2.98 and students of co-education schools had mean of 2.98 at pretest. At posttest, single-sex school students had 2.99 mean and co-education school students had 2.99 mean. There was a rise in mean of students at posttest in all the methods and the slight difference in mean is in favour of single-sex school students. In addition, this table shows a mean difference of 0.03 in learning attitude in favour of

single-sex school students taught with lecture teaching method and a mean difference of 0.11 in learning attitude in favour of co-education school students taught with lecture teaching method at pretest. At post, a mean difference of 0.06 in learning attitude in favour of single-sex school students taught with demonstration teaching method and a mean difference of 0.09 in learning attitude in favour of co-education school students taught with lecture teaching method. Also, a mean difference of 0.16 in learning attitude in favour of single-sex school students taught with lecture teaching method and a mean difference of 0.04 in learning attitude in favour of co-education school students taught with lecture teaching method at pretest. At posttest, a mean difference of 0.11 in learning attitude in favour of single-sex school students taught with discussion teaching method and a mean difference of 0.03 in learning attitude in favour of co-education school students taught with lecture teaching method.

Research Question 2

What difference exist between the mean retention scores of SS2 students in single-sex and co-education schools taught Biology using demonstration and discussion methods?

Table 2: Summary Mean Retention Test and Retention Level of SS2 Students in Coeducational and Single-Sex Schools Taught Biology via Demonstration, Discussion and Lecture Methods.

Teaching Method	School Type	N	Retention Test \bar{x}	Posttest \bar{x}	RL \bar{x}	Diff in RL \bar{x}
Demonstration	Single-sex	51	55.58	45.92	9.66	1.42
	Co-education	70	59.02	47.94	11.08	
Difference			3.44	2.02		
Discussion	Single-sex	26	70.11	62.11	8.00	6.27
	Co-education	89	68.04	53.77	14.27	
Difference			2.07	8.34		
Demonstration	Single-sex	51	55.58	45.92	9.66	9.00
		Lecture	27	51.66	51.00	
Difference			3.92	5.08		
Demonstration	Co-education	70	59.02	47.94	11.08	1.06
		Lecture	60	70.90	58.76	
Difference			11.88	10.82		
Discussion	Single-sex	26	70.11	62.11	8.00	7.34
		Lecture	27	51.66	51.00	
Difference			18.45	11.11		
Discussion	Co-education	89	68.04	53.77	14.27	2.13
		Lecture	60	70.90	58.76	
Difference			2.86	4.99		

Answer to research question two, Table 2 shows single-sex retention level (9.66) and co-education school students mean retention level (11.08) when taught with demonstration method with a

difference of 1.42 in favour of co-education schools students. When taught with discussion method, single-sex mean retention level (8.00) and co-education mean retention level (14.27) had a difference of 6.27 in favour of co-education school students. When taught with lecture method, single-sex mean retention level (0.66) and co-education school students mean retention level (12.14) had a difference of 11.48 in favour of co-education school students. The Table shows that co-education school students had higher retention level than single-sex school students. In addition, the table shows a difference of 9.33 retention level mean in favour of single-sex school students taught with demonstration teaching method and a difference of 1.06 retention level mean in favour of co-education school students taught with lecture teaching method. Also, a difference of 7.34 retention level mean in favour of single-sex school students taught with discussion teaching method and a difference of 2.13 retention level mean in favour of co-education school students taught with discussion teaching method.

Hypotheses 1

There is no significant difference between the mean attitude scores of SS2 students in single-sex and co-education schools, taught Biology using demonstration and discussion methods.

Table 3: Summary of z- test Analysis of Single-sex and Co-education Schools SS2 Students Attitude taught using Demonstration, Discussion and Lecture Methods.

Teaching Method	School Type	N	Post Attitude \bar{x}	SD	df	Z _{cal}	Z _{crit}	Type of test	P
Demonstration	Single-sex	51	3.05	0.97	119	0.9	1.96	2-tailed	<0.05
	Co-education	70	2.90	0.77					
Discussion	Single-sex	26	3.10	1.29	113	0.5	1.96	2-tailed	<0.05
	Co-education	89	2.96	0.71					
Demonstration	Single-sex	51	3.05	0.97	76	0.23	1.98	2-tailed	<0.05
	Lecture	27	2.99	1.22					
Demonstration	Single-sex	70	2.90	0.77	128	0.63	1.96	2-tailed	<0.05
	Co-education	60	2.99	0.88					
Lecture	Single-sex	26	3.10	1.29	51	0.33	1.98	2-tailed	<0.05
	Discussion	27	2.99	1.22					
Lecture	Single-sex	89	2.96	0.71	147	0.23	1.96	2-tailed	<0.05
	Co-education	60	2.99	0.88					

When hypothesis 1, H₀₁, was subjected to z-test examination, as in Table 3, it was observed that the z-calculated value is 0.9 while the z-critical value is 1.96 when taught with demonstration teaching method. The null hypothesis is hereby accepted while the alternate hypothesis is rejected because the calculated z-value is smaller than the z-critical value. This implies that there is no substantial variance in the mean scores of single sex and co-education school students in learning attitude in Biology when taught with demonstration teaching method. It was also observed that the

calculated z-value is 0.5 while the z-critical value is 1.96 when taught with discussion teaching method. The null hypothesis is hereby accepted while the alternate hypothesis is rejected because the calculated z-value is smaller than the z-critical value. This implies that there is no substantial variance in the mean scores of single sex and co-education school students in learning attitude in Biology when taught with discussion teaching method.

It was also observed that the calculated z-value is 0.23 while the z-critical value is 1.98 when taught with demonstration and lecture teaching methods. The null hypothesis is hereby accepted while the alternate hypothesis because the calculated z-value is smaller than the z-critical value. This implies that there is no substantial variance in the mean scores of single sex school students in learning attitude in Biology when taught with demonstration and lecture teaching methods. It was also observed that the calculated z-value is 0.63 while the z-critical value is 1.96 when taught with demonstration and lecture teaching methods. The null hypothesis is hereby accepted while the alternate hypothesis is rejected because the calculated z-value is smaller than the z-critical value. This implies that there is no substantial variance in the mean scores of co-education school students in learning attitude in Biology when taught with demonstration and lecture teaching methods.

It was also observed that the calculated z-value is 0.33 while the z-critical value is 1.98 when taught with discussion and lecture teaching methods. The null hypothesis is hereby accepted while the alternate hypothesis is rejected because the calculated z-value is smaller than the z-critical value. This implies that there is no substantial variance in the mean scores of single sex school students in learning attitude in Biology when taught with discussion and lecture teaching methods. It was also observed that the calculated z-value is 0.23 while the z-critical value is 1.96 when taught with discussion and lecture teaching methods. The null hypothesis is hereby accepted while the alternate hypothesis is rejected because the calculated z-value is smaller than the z-critical value. This implies that there is no substantial variance in the mean scores of co-education school students in learning attitude in Biology when taught with discussion and lecture teaching methods.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between the mean retention scores of SS2 students in single-sex and co-education schools, taught Biology using demonstration and discussion methods.

Table 4: Summary of z- test Analysis of Single-sex and Co-education Schools SS2 Students Retention Level taught using Demonstration, Discussion and Lecture Methods.

Teaching Method	Sch Type	N	Retention Level \bar{x}	SD	df	Z _{cal}	Z _{crit}	Type of test	P
Demonstration	Single-sex	51	9.66	12.26	119	0.63	1.96	2-tailed	<0.05
	Co-education	70	11.08	12.22					
Discussion	Single-sex	26	8.00	9.49	113	2.90	1.96	2-tailed	<0.05
	Co-education	89	14.27	10.42					
Demonstration	Single-sex	27	0.66	14.61	76	2.73	1.98	2-tailed	<0.05
	Co-education	70	11.08	12.22					
Lecture	Single-sex	27	0.66	14.61	128	0.38	1.96	2-tailed	<0.05
	Co-education	60	12.14	18.04					
Discussion	Single-sex	26	8.00	9.49	51	2.17	1.98	2-tailed	<0.05
	Co-education	89	14.27	10.42					
Lecture	Co-education	60	12.14	18.04	147	0.82	1.96	2-tailed	<0.05

When hypothesis 2, H₀₂, was subjected to z-test examination, in Table 4, it was revealed that the z-calculated value is 0.63 and the z-critical value is 1.96 when taught with demonstration teaching method. The null hypothesis is accepted while the alternate hypothesis is rejected since the z-calculated value is smaller than the z-critical value. This implies that there is no substantial variance in the mean scores of students in single sex and co-education schools taught with demonstration teaching method in retention level in Biology. It was also discovered in table 4 that the z-calculated value is 2.90 and the z-critical is 1.96 when taught with discussion method. The null hypothesis is rejected while the alternate hypothesis is accepted since the z-calculated value is bigger than the z-critical. This implies that there is a substantial variance in the mean scores of students in single sex and co-education schools taught with discussion method in retention level in Biology to the advantage of students in co-education senior schools.

It was also discovered in table 4 that the z-calculated value is 2.73 and the z-critical is 1.98 when taught with demonstration and lecture teaching methods. The null hypothesis is rejected while the alternate hypothesis is accepted since the z-calculated value is bigger than the z-critical value. This implies that there is a substantial variance in the mean scores of students in single sex schools taught with demonstration and lecture teaching methods in retention level enhancement in Biology. It was revealed that the z-calculated value is 0.38 and the z-critical value is 1.96 when taught with demonstration and lecture teaching methods. The null hypothesis is accepted while the alternate hypothesis is rejected since the z-calculated value is smaller than the z-critical value. This implies that there is no substantial variance in the mean scores of students in co-education schools taught with demonstration and lecture teaching methods in retention level in Biology.

It was also discovered in Table 4 that the z-calculated value is 2.17 and the z-critical is 1.98 when taught with discussion and lecture teaching methods. The null hypothesis is rejected while the alternate hypothesis is accepted since the z-calculated value is bigger than the z-critical value. This implies that there is a substantial variance in the mean scores of students in single sex schools taught with discussion and lecture teaching methods in retention level in Biology. It was revealed that the z-calculated value is 0.82 and the z-critical value is 1.96 when taught with discussion and lecture teaching methods. The null hypothesis is accepted while the alternate hypothesis is rejected since the z-calculated value is smaller than the z-critical value. This implies that there is no substantial variance in the mean scores of students in co-education schools taught with discussion and lecture teaching methods in retention level in Biology.

Discussions

From research question one, single-sex and co-education schools' students had increase in learning attitude when taught with demonstration, discussion and lecture teaching methods in all the groups but when subjected to z-test probing, results showed non-substantial in all the groups. There is no significant difference in the mean scores of SS2 students in single-sex and co-education schools in attitude when taught with demonstration, discussion and lecture teaching methods in Biology. This is probably because teachers of equal standing in terms of academic qualification and experience taught them and uniform topics and lesson notes were used to teach students in the single-sex and co-education schools. Also, single-sex students have fear of being discriminated against and poor communication skill which militate against their learning attitude and academic achievement. This study is in disagreement with Ademe (2016). He reported that co-education school students have better learning attitude than single-sex school students.

From research question two, co-education school students taught with demonstration teaching method had higher retention level than single-sex school students taught with demonstration teaching method but when subjected to z-test analysis, result showed non-substantial. There is no significant difference in the mean scores of SS2 students in single-sex and co-education schools taught with demonstration method in retention level in Biology. This implies that there is a substantial link among academic achievement, retention level and school type. This is probably because the teachers in senior schools are of equal standing in terms of academic qualifications and experience. When academic achievement is high, there is possibility that retention level will be high and they are not dependent on school type according to Isah et al, (2019). Also, co-education school students taught with discussion teaching method had remarkable retention level than single-sex school students taught with discussion teaching method and when subjected to z-test analysis, result showed substantial. There is a significant difference in the mean scores of SS2 students in single-sex and co-education schools taught with discussion method in retention level in Biology. This is in agreement with Egbule (as cited in Oghenevwede, 2012). He observed that the higher the students' participation the better the learning and level of retention. This is probably because of gender-free discriminating environment that promote high socialization level in the co-education schools which enhances active participation of students, interaction and exchange of ideas, hence, enhanced retention level.

From research question two, single-sex school students taught with demonstration teaching method had remarkable retention level than single-sex school students taught with lecture teaching method and when subjected to z-test analysis, result showed substantial. There is a substantial variance in the mean scores of students in single-sex schools taught with demonstration and lecture

teaching methods in retention level in Biology. This is probably because demonstration teaching method gives room for display of lesson and practical session which explains concept better for proper understanding than lecture teaching method. This agrees with the work of Veselinovska (2011) who stated that learners recall 20% of what they hear, 10% of what they read, 30% of what they say and 90% of what they had on hands on experience and Ameh & Dantani (2012). Co-education school students taught with lecture teaching method had higher retention level than co-education school students taught with demonstration teaching method but when subjected to z-probing, result showed non-substantial.

Also, from research question two, single-sex school students taught with discussion teaching method had remarkable retention level than single-sex school students taught with lecture teaching method and when subjected to z-test probing, result showed substantial. There is a substantial variance in the mean scores of students in single-sex schools taught with discussion and lecture teaching methods in retention level in Biology. This is probably because discussion teaching method gives room for independent thought and exchange of ideas among students which enhances understanding and increases retention level. This agrees with the work of Albert et al, (2014) and Basil & Jajua (2019). Also, co-education school students taught with discussion teaching method had higher retention than co-education school students taught with lecture teaching method but when subjected to z-test probing, result showed non-substantial. There is no substantial variance in the mean scores of students in co-education schools taught with discussion and lecture teaching method in retention level in Biology.

Conclusion

The study examined effect of teaching methods on attitude and retention of single-sex and co-education students in senior school biology. It revealed that method of teaching used in teaching and learning process is important in students' attitude and retention of biology. There is no significant difference in the mean scores of SS2 students in single-sex and co-education schools in attitude when taught with demonstration, discussion and lecture teaching methods in Biology. Also, no significant difference in the mean scores of SS2 students in single-sex and co-education schools taught with demonstration method in retention in Biology. This implies that there is a substantial link among academic achievement, retention level and school type.

Reference

- Adebanjo, A. A. & Yusuf, S. A. (2023). Effect of lecture method supplemented with computer animation package on secondary school students' achievement in biology. *Journal of Curriculum Organization of Nigeria*, 30(2), 1-16.
- Achimugu, L. (2018). Effectiveness of enriched demonstration and lecture instructional strategies on senior secondary school students' achievement in chemistry. *Journal of Contemporary Education Research*, 246, 2(1). <http://doi.org/10.26689/jcer.v2i1>.
- Ademe, E. (2016). Single-gender or mixed -gender? All-boys and all-girls school students' attitude towards single-sex schooling. *Ethiopian Journal of Development Research*, 38(2). <https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&source=web&rct=j&opi=89978449&url=https://www.ajol.info/index.php/ejdr/article/view/185309&ved=2ahUKEwiz0Kbmqe-GAxXKZkEAHQFUAYYQFnoECBMQAQ&usg=AOvVaw0g4L-51FO4Fu8wnMwbJ0Qb>
- Ahmad, R. N. & Asghar S. K. (2011). Attitude towards biology and its effects on students' achievement. *International Journal of Biology*, 3(4), 100-104. <https://www.researchg>

ate.net/publication/266870153_Attitude_towards_Biology_and_Its_Effects_on_Student%27s_Achievement

- Akuezuilo, E. O. & Agu, N. (2004). *Research and Statistics in Education & Social Sciences: Methods and Applications*. Awka, Nigeria: Nuel Centi Publishers and Academic Press Ltd.
- Albert, O. O., Osman, A., & Yungungu, A. (2014). An investigation of factors that influence performance in KSCE biology in selected secondary schools in Nyakach District, Kisumu County Kenya. *Journal of Education and Human Development*, 3(2), 957-977. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/An-investigation-of-Factors-that-Influence-in-KCSE-Albert-Osman/8ad4a05101307c7f25bb2451a1cbd7ae3f586e61>
- Ali, A.R., Toriman, M. E., & Gasim, M. B. (2014). Academic achievement in biology with suggested solutions in selected secondary schools in Kano State. *Nigeria International Journal of Education and Research*, 2(11), 215-224. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/281147427_Academic_Achievement_in_Biology_with_Suggested_Solutions_in_Selected_Secondary_Schools_in_Kano_State_Nigeria
- Ameh, P. O. & Dantani, Y. S. (2012). Effects of lecture and demonstration methods on the academic achievement of students in chemistry in Nasarawa Local Government Area in Kano State. *International Journal of Modern Social Sciences*, 1(1),29-37. https://www.academia.edu/30214517/Effects_of_Lecture_and_Demonstration_Methods_on_the_Academic_Achievement_of_Students_in_Chemistry_in_Nassarawa_Local_Government_Area_of_Kano_State
- Arokoyu, A. A. & Chukwu, J. C. (2017). Biology teachers' methods of teaching and academic performance of secondary school students in Abia state. *Journal of Emerging Trends in Educational Research and Policy Studies*, 8(4), 228-231. 839X. 1-9. Retrieved from <http://cie.asu.edu/ojs/index.php/cieatasu/article/view/809>.
- Badmus, O. T. & Omosewo, E. O. (2018). Improving science education in Nigeria: The role of key stakeholders. *European Journal of Health and Biology Education*, 1-5. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/324533974_Improving_Science_Education_in_Nigeria_The_Role_of_Key_Stakeholders
- Bandura, A., Ross, D. & Ross, S. (1961). Transmission of aggression through imitation of aggression models. *Journal of Abnormal and Social Psychology*, 63. 575-582
- Basila, D. & Jajua, M. A. (2019). Effects of demonstration and discussion strategies on secondary school students' achievement and retention in biology in Mubi educational zone, Adamawa state. *International Journal of Research and Scientific Innovation*, 6(12), 234-246. <https://www.rsisinternational.org/journals/ijrsi/digital-library/volume-6-issue-12/234-246.pdf>
- Campbell, D. T., Stanley, J. C. & Gage, N. L. (1963). *Experimental and quasi-experimental designs for research*. Boston: Houghton Mifflin.
- Cohen, L., Manion, L. & Morrison, K. (2011). *Research methods in Education*. Library of Congress Cataloguing-in-publication data.
- Egbule, J. F. (2002). *Fundamentals of Test, Measurement and Evaluation*. (Second Edition). Owerri: Whyte and whyte publishers.
- Gambari, A. I., Yaki, A. A., Gana, E. S., & Ughovwa, Q. E. (2014). Improving secondary school student s' achievement and retention in biology through video-based multimedia instruction. *Journal of Scholarly Teaching*, 9,78-91. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1035855.pdf>
- Gongden, E. J. (2022). Improving chemistry students' achievement and retention in chemical kinetics using blended learning strategy in Jos- Plateau State, Nigeria. *International Journal*

- of Education and Evaluation, 8(6), 33-42. <https://www.iiardjournals.org/abstract.php?j=IJEE&pn=Improving%20Chemistry%20Students%E2%80%99%20Achievement%20and%20Retentionin%20Chemical%20Kinetics%20Using%20Blended%20Learning%20Strategy%20inJos%20-Plateau%20State,%20Nigeria&id=3172>. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.56201/ijee.v8.no6.2022.pg33.42>
- Hussaini, I., Foong, L. M., & Kamar, Y. (2015). Attitudes of senior secondary school students towards biology as a school subject in Birin Kebbi metropolis Nigeria. *International Journal of Research and Review*, 596-600. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/283515328_Attitudes_of_Secondary_School_Students_towards_Biology_as_a_School_Subject_in_Birin_kebbi_Metropolis_Nigeria
- Igbojinwaekwu, P. C. (2012a). Gender differences and enrollment in senior certificate examination chemistry. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Research Development*, 18(1), 1-5.
- Igbojinwaekwu, P. C. & Torunarigha, Y. D. (2012). Academic performance of girls in single-sex and co-education schools in senior school mathematics in Delta state Capital Territory. *Journal of Assertiveness*, 1(1), 139-144. <https://www.globalacademicgroup.com/journals/assertiveness/ACADEMIC%20PERFORMANCE%20OF%20GIRLS%20IN%20SINGLE-SEX%20AND.pdf>
- Isah, Y.A., Murja, D. I., & Yunusa, F. U. (2019). School type and academic achievement in biology among senior secondary school students in Zaria, Nigeria: Analysis of difference and relationship. *Journal of Science Technology and Education*, 7(4), 156-160.
- McLeod, S. A. (2018). *Jean Piaget's theory of cognitive development*. Simply Psychology. <https://www.simplypsychology.org/piaget.htmlss>
- McLeod, S. A. (2019). *Constructivism as a theory for teaching and learning*. Simply Psychology. <https://www.Simplypsychology.org/constructivism.html>
- Ndu, F. O. C., Okeke, S. O. C., & Igbojinwaekwu, P. C. (2005). Competitive learning environment and academic achievement in mathematics of girls in senior secondary science. *International Journal of FAWE, Nigeria*, 1(3), 154-160.
- Oghenevwe, O. E. (2012). Enhancing the retention level of biology students through the guided discovery instructional method. *Nigerian Journal of Curriculum and Instruction*, 19(1), 7-12.
- Oginni, A. M., Awobodu, V. Y., Alaka, M. O., & Saidu, S. O. (2013). School factors as correlates of students' achievement in chemistry. *International Journal for Cross Disciplinary Subjects in education*, 3(3), 1516-1523. <https://infonomics-society.org/wp-content/uploads/ijcdse/published-papers/special-issue-volume-3-2013/School-Factors-as-Correlates-of-Students-Achievement-in-Chemistry.pdf>
- Ogunleye, B. O & Fasakin, A. O. (2011). Everyday phenomena in physics education: Impact on male and female students' achievement, attitude and practical skills in urban and peri-urban settings in Nigeria. *Pakistan Journal of Social Sciences* 8, 316-324. https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=en&user=UK-FZvUAAAAJ&citation_for_view=UK-FZvUAAAAJ:zYLM7Y9cAGgC
- Samikwo, D. C. (2013). Factors which influence academic performance in biology in Kenya: a perspective for global competitiveness. *International Journal of Current Research*, 5(12), 4296-4300. <https://www.journalcra.com/article/factors-which-influence-academic-performance-biology-kenya-perspective-global-competitiveness>

- Teba, S. C. (2020). Exploring the impact of single-sex education on Beninese Eft advanced students' academic achievement: Case study of Lycee De jeunes filles Toffa 1. *Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 29-38. <https://iosrjournals.org/iosr-jhss/papers/Vol.25-Issue8/Series-12/C2508122938.pdf>
- Thyer, B. A. (2012). *Quasi-experimental research designs*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Veselinovska, S. S. (2011). The effect of teaching methods on cognitive achievement, retention and attitude among biology students. *Cypriot Journal of Educational Sciences*, 4, 175-185. [www. World-education-center.org/index.php/cjes](http://www.world-education-center.org/index.php/cjes).
- West African Examination Council. (2022). Chief Examiner's Report. Lagos